

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POLY(1,4 BUTYLENE CARBONATE-CO-TEREPHTHALATE)/ORGANICALLY MODIFIED LAYERED DOUBLE HYDROXIDES NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Poly(1,4 butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT)/organically modified layered double hydroxide (m-LDH) nanocomposites were successfully synthesized with a solution blending method. PBCT, a semi-crystalline and biodegradable copolymer, had been synthesized via a two-step procedure using sodium hydroxide as a catalyst. In order to improve the compatibility with PBCT, the LDH was modified by the intercalation of octanoic acid and stearic acid into interlayer space using co-precipitation method (OA-LDH, SA-LDH), respectively. X-ray diffraction (XRD) revealed that the modification of LDH resulted in significantly increased of the interlayer distance. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FT-IR) studies showed that m-LDH contained both functional groups of organical modifier and LDH. The diffraction peaks of PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites at lower angle were extremely weak and board, indicating that OA-LDH layers formed a mixed of intercalated and exfoliated conformation in nanocomposites. However, in PBCT/SA-LDH nanocomposites, SA-LDH layers were fully exfoliated. Isothermal crystallization behavior of neat PBCT and 1, 3, 5 wt% PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The half-time for crystallization of nanocomposites decreased with the OA-LDH content, indicating that filler acted as a heterogeneous point which caused an increase in the crystallization rate. Nevertheless, the result of nanocomposites with the SA-LDH content is the opposite to that of OA-LDH, owing to the huge size of stearic anion on the LDH surface served as a barrier to hinder the motion of polymer chain.

Experiment

Characterization results

Isothermal crystallization

